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BEEWATCHING: CITIZEN SCIENCE ON BEES

Beewatching: citizen science con le api

Citizen science (CS) is the involvement of the public in scientific research, through the collection of data by volunteer members (HAKLAY *et al.*, 2021): the advantage is to allow the collection of a large amount of data over wide areas, which would otherwise not be possible if conducted by paid professionals (PATEMAN *et al.*, 2021). To start an effective CS project, the dissemination of information is essential, to reach as many people as possible, who will act as citizen scientists. The use of Internet has broadened the chance for public engagement. Internet, in fact, allows the spreading of real-time information and give citizens the possibility to make immediate reports, insert data and upload photos. Given the importance of bees for the maintenance of ecosystem health (OLLERTON *et al.*, 2011), their current state of risk and consequent growing popularity among people, it is becoming urgent to develop monitoring systems that allow even non-professionals to return relevant data to scientists. Bee-watching is a citizen science project started in spring 2018 from a collaboration between CREA (Council for Agricultural Research and Economics) and the BiGeA Department (University of Bologna). The project target is to acquire information on wild bee species in Italy and to promote knowledge among citizens on the diversity of bees and their importance as pollinators. Moreover, a secondary target is to follow the distribution of two alien bee species present in Italy, *Megachile sculpturalis* Smith, 1853 (QUARANTA *et al.*, 2014) and *Megachile disjunctiformis* Cock-

erell, 1911 (BORTOLOTTI *et al.*, 2018). Here we report the results obtained after three years of project (2019-2021), to verify how far the project has spread on the Italian territory, and assess the progress achieved in terms of participation and identification skills. The first step of the project was to create a website platform (www.beewatching.it, accessed on 25 March 2022) providing a section with informative datasheets of the wild bee families and common bee genera present in Italy. The cores of the website are the form to send reports of observed bees and the interactive map which shows all citizen's reports. The form to enter the reports requires the following data: name, surname, and e-mail address of the reporter; one or more photos of the bee; the date of the photographs; the indication of a size class: XS, Extremely Small (4–6 mm); S, Small (6–8 mm); M, Medium (8–13 mm); L, Large (13–16 mm); XL, Extra Large (>16 mm), locality. Furthermore, the form includes two fields where the reporter can enter a tentative taxonomic identification of the bee and the visited flower. All the reports sent to the website were verified by experts and any erroneous attribution on bee and plant species were corrected; once the photo was sent, the participants received feedback. The project followed a circular process through four different steps: a “passive” training through the videos and the on-line datasheets on bee genera and species; data collection through the photo sent by the beewatchers; data verification by project experts; and data analysis.

The data obtained in three years of activity of the project were classified according to the year of the report, the province and region of origin, the size (presumed) of the bee specimen, the genus, and, when possible, the species of the photographed bee. Given the difficulty of identifying bees to the rank of species by the photograph, the identification by the users was considered correct when the assignment to the genus rank was correct. A χ^2 was calculated to verify if the number of correct bee identification by users increases over the three years.

In three years, we received 2333 reports, with a clear increase through the years, starting from 349 reports in 2019 to 1212 in 2021. The most reported genus is *Bombus* Latreille 1802 with 454 reports, in line with the most widely reported size class, which is the Medium M size (1124 reports). Correct reports increase from 199 in 2019 to 775 in 2021, and the chi-square test shows a statistically significant difference (χ^2 , $p = 0.039656$).

Reports are well distributed over the national territory, and the region with the most reports is Sicily (491 reports), while the region with the fewest reports is Molise (6 reports); there were no reports from Valle d'Aosta and Basilicata.

Megachile sculpturalis has been reported 74 times, including some first reports for Southern Italy, but no report has been received for *M. disjunctiformis*.

The first three years of the Beewatching project led to some positive results, namely the increasing number of reports, a greater distribution of reports throughout the country and the percentage of correct ones increasing during three years of the project. Furthermore, the reports relating to *M. sculpturalis* have led to a broadening of knowledge about the distribution of this species. A report was also received of a species of the family Andrenidae (*Andrena binominata* Smith 1853) observed very rarely in Italy. However, there are still some improvements that can be made in the next years: it might be interesting to outline the profile of “beewatchers” through a questionnaire and to start some sub-projects for conservation purposes (DOMROESE & JOHNSON, 2017; SAUNDERS *et al.*, 2018).

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